

University of Venda

RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE

UNIVEN Informed Consent

Appendix B

LETTER OF INFORMATION

Title of the Research Study: The complexities of maternal non-adherence to antiretroviral therapy and its impact on mother-to-child transmission in Capricorn District, Limpopo Province.

Principal Investigator/s/ researcher: Enicca Phillipine Mkhondo

Co-Investigator/s/supervisor/s: Dr. A.G Mudau

Brief Introduction and Purpose of the Study

HIV/AIDS remains a significant public health challenge, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa. The Prevention of Mother-to-Child Transmission (PMTCT) of HIV is a key strategy in reducing new infections among children, and adherence to antiretroviral therapy (ART) is central to achieving this goal. However, despite the availability of ART, many HIV-positive mothers fail to adhere to treatment regimens during pregnancy or when breastfeeding their infants, placing both their own health and the health of their children at risk.

The purpose of this study is to explore the complexities surrounding maternal non-adherence to ART and its impact on the transmission of HIV from mother to child (MTCT) in the Capricorn District, Limpopo Province. This research aims to understand the personal, socio-economic, and systemic barriers contributing to ART non-adherence, as well as to assess its implications on the prevention of mother-to-child transmission of HIV. Through in-depth unstructured interviews with HIV-positive pregnant or breastfeeding mothers and nursing professionals at local health facilities, this study also seeks to identify key factors influencing adherence, as well as potential interventions or improvements that could enhance ART uptake and reduce MTCT rates in the district.

Outline of the Procedures

This qualitative study will explore the lived experiences of HIV-positive mothers who are not adhering to antiretroviral therapy (ART), as well as perspectives from nursing professionals in selected clinics in the Capricorn District. The procedures outlined below detail the responsibilities of participants and the methods that will be employed:

Participant Responsibilities

Participants will be asked to engage in a one-on-one, in-depth, unstructured interview. They will be expected to openly share their personal experiences, perceptions, and challenges related to ART non-adherence, either from a lived (mother) or professional (manager) perspective.

Interview Details

- **HIV-positive mothers** will participate in unstructured, face-to-face interviews lasting approximately 45 to 60 minutes. These interviews will allow participants to guide the conversation, highlighting issues most relevant to their lived experiences.
- **Nursing professionals** will also be engaged through unstructured interviews, with a focus on their professional observations, clinic-level challenges, and recommendations concerning maternal ART adherence.

Interviews will be conducted in a private setting at the respective clinics to ensure confidentiality and participant comfort.

Venue Details

All interviews will be conducted at selected health facilities within Capricorn District. Interview appointments will be scheduled to align with participants' regular antenatal or postnatal clinic visits to reduce logistical and economic burden.

Inclusion Criteria

HIV-Positive Mothers: To be eligible for participation, mothers must be 18 years of age or older and either currently pregnant or within the postpartum period, defined as having given birth within the past 12 months. This timeframe is considered critical for interventions aimed at the prevention of mother-to-child transmission (PMTCT) of HIV. Eligible participants must be HIV-positive and identified as inconsistently non-adherent to ART, either through clinical records or by healthcare provider referral. To ensure the study explores long-term challenges associated with adherence, only those who have been on ART for a minimum of six months will be included. Furthermore, eligible mothers must reside in the Capricorn District and access healthcare services at public health facilities within the district. Participation is voluntary and subject to informed consent.

Nursing professionals: Nursing professionals will be selected from clinics identified by the Limpopo Department of Health as having high rates of maternal ART non-adherence. Eligible nursing professionals must be employed by the Department of Health and stationed within the Capricorn District. To ensure sufficient depth of experience and insight, participants must have served in their ART management role for at least two years. Both male and female nursing professionals will be considered. As with the mothers, their participation is contingent upon their willingness to take part and the signing of informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria

HIV-Positive Mothers

- Mothers who have been recently initiated on ART, as the study focuses on exploring challenges with long-term adherence, which requires a minimum duration of treatment experience.
- Mothers with medical or psychological conditions, such as cognitive impairments or untreated mental health conditions, that may compromise their ability to give informed consent or participate in the interview process meaningfully.
- Mothers who do not reside within the Capricorn District or who access healthcare services outside the district, as the study is geographically bound to this location.

Nursing professionals

- Those who are currently on leave or otherwise unavailable during the data collection period, as their absence would limit their ability to participate in scheduled interviews.
- Nursing professionals temporarily assigned to clinics in the Capricorn District for special projects or interim duties, but who are not officially stationed or employed in the district on a permanent basis. These individuals may lack the contextual experience required for the study.
- Nursing professionals with less than two years of work experience as the study requires insights drawn from a sustained period of professional engagement in ART service delivery.

Explanation of Tools and Measurement Outcomes

Unstructured data collection tools will be used. The unstructured interviews will enable participants to express themselves freely without predetermined constraints. Conversations will be audio-recorded (with informed consent) and later transcribed for qualitative analysis. Thematic content will be analyzed to identify recurring patterns, beliefs, and systemic barriers related to ART adherence and MTCT.

- **Follow-up:** Follow-up interviews are not planned but may be arranged if necessary for clarification, and only with participant consent. No ongoing interventions or monitoring will occur after the initial data collection.
- **Placebo or No Treatment:** As this is a non-intervention, observational study, there will be no use of placebos, treatments, or experimental procedures.
- **Time Commitment:** Participation requires a one-time commitment of approximately 45 to 60 minutes during the participant's routine clinic visit. Additional time will only be requested if further clarification is needed and agreed upon.
- **Expectations of Participants:** Participants are expected to engage sincerely and honestly during the interview, focusing on their personal or professional experiences with ART adherence. Participation is voluntary, and participants have the right to decline any questions or withdraw at any time without any negative consequences or loss of healthcare services.

- **Randomization or Group Allocation:** This study does not involve randomization or group assignment. Participants are selected purposively based on their relevance to the study focus and criteria.

Risks or Discomforts to the Participant

The study presents minimal risk to participants. However, the following potential risks have been identified, and appropriate mitigation strategies will be implemented:

- **Physical Fatigue:** Participants may experience fatigue due to sitting for the duration of the interview. This risk will be minimized by allowing a five-minute leg-stretching break should the participant feel tired.
- **Emotional Discomfort or Distress:** Discussing personal experiences related to non-adherence to ART may evoke emotional discomfort or psychological distress. To mitigate this, a registered counsellor or social worker will be on standby to provide telephonic counselling and support if needed.
- **Economic Burden:** Participants may be concerned about potential transport costs associated with attending interviews. This risk will be addressed by aligning data collection dates with participants' scheduled antenatal or postnatal clinic visits. The researcher will conduct interviews at the clinics, thereby eliminating additional transport expenses.
- **Uncertainty Regarding Responses:** Participants may feel uncertain about how to respond to interview questions. To address this, participants will be provided with the interview guide one week prior to the interview to allow for adequate preparation. Participation remains voluntary, and participants will be informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any point without penalty.

Benefits

To Participants: While there are no direct financial or material benefits, participants may benefit indirectly through psychological relief or empowerment by sharing their experiences. The study may also contribute to improved health services and support structures for HIV-positive mothers in the future.

To the Researcher: The researcher will benefit academically by fulfilling partial requirements for a Master of Public Health degree. In addition, the findings may lead to scholarly publications, contributing to the academic body of knowledge on ART adherence and informing future policy and intervention strategies aimed at improving PMTCT outcomes.

Reason/s why the Participant May Be Withdrawn from the Study

Participants may be withdrawn from the study under the following circumstances:

- At their own request, at any point without providing a reason.
- If the principal investigator determines that continued participation may pose a risk to the participant's well-being.

- If a participant displays signs of distress that cannot be ethically or safely managed during the data collection process.
- If the participant engages in behaviour that compromises the safety or confidentiality of others involved in the study.

Remuneration

No financial remuneration will be provided to participants. However, they will be provided with water and snacks after the interviews as a courtesy for their participation and time spent.

Costs of the Study

There will be no costs incurred by participants for participation, as interviews will be conducted during scheduled clinic visits to avoid additional expenses.

Confidentiality

All information gathered during the study will be kept confidential. The researcher will ensure that participants' identities are protected by using pseudonyms in all study records and reports. No identifying information will be linked to any data in the final analysis. Audio recordings will be securely stored and transcribed by the researcher alone. All hard copy and electronic data will be kept in a locked file or password-protected device accessible only to the researcher. Additionally, the collected data, including audio recordings will be securely stored for a minimum of five years after the completion of the study, in accordance with ethical guidelines and institutional requirements.

Data Re-use

Please note: The data collected during this study may be stored securely and reused in future related studies by the same researcher, if all identifying information is removed and confidentiality is maintained. Participation in this study does not automatically enrol you in future studies, and any future use of the data will remain within the ethical boundaries of confidentiality and informed consent.

Participant choice regarding future data use (please tick one):

- I agree that my de-identified data may be used for future related research.
- I do not agree that my data may be used for any future research.

Research-related Injury

There are no expected risks of physical injury during participation. The study involves interviews with no physical procedures. However, if a participant experiences emotional discomfort or distress while discussing their experiences with ART adherence, they will be offered immediate psychological support. A registered counsellor or social worker will be on standby to provide telephonic counselling if needed.

Persons to Contact in the Event of Any Problems or Queries:

Please contact the researcher, Ms. Enicca Phillipine Mkhondo (071 644 0460/ mkhondophilipine@gmail.com), my supervisor, Dr. A.G. Mudau (015 962 8601/ azwindinni.mudau@univen.ac.za). University Research Ethics Committee Secretariat on 015 962 9058 / Vanecia.Khoza@univen.ac.za

Complaints can be reported to the University Research Ethics Committee Secretariat on 015 962 9058 / Vanecia.Khoza@univen.ac.za or Whistle blowing Ethics Hotline Tollfree Telephone number: 0800212755 Email.univenhotline@tipoffs.com

General:
Potential participants must be assured that participation is voluntary and the approximate number of participants to be included should be disclosed. A copy of the information letter should be issued to participants. The information letter and consent form must be translated and provided in the primary spoken language of the research population

CONSENT

Statement of Agreement to Participate in the Research Study:

- I hereby confirm that I have been informed by the researcher, Enicca Phillipine Mkhondo, about the nature, conduct, benefits and risks of this study - Research Ethics Clearance Number: **FHS/25/PH/13/3107**.
- I have also received, read and understood the above written information (*Participant Letter of Information*) regarding the study.
- I am aware that the results of the study, including personal details regarding my sex, age, date of birth, initials and diagnosis will be anonymously processed into a study report.
- In view of the requirements of research, I agree that the data collected during this study can be processed in a computerized system by the researcher.
- I may, at any stage, without prejudice, withdraw my consent and participation in the study.
- I have had sufficient opportunity to ask questions and (of my own free will) declare myself prepared to participate in the study.
- I understand that significant new findings developed during the course of this research which may relate to my participation will be made available to me.

Full Name of Participant	Date	Time	Signature
I,

(Name of researcher) herewith confirm that the above participant has been fully Informed about the nature, conduct and risks of the above study.

Full Name of Researcher.....

Date.....

Signature.....

Full Name of Witness (If applicable)

.....

Date

Signature.....

Full Name of Legal Guardian (If applicable)

.....

Date.....

Signature.....

